

Geography in Scientific Practice and Country Biases

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Abstract

Recent decades witnessed a steady increase in international scientific collaboration, alongside debates on nationalist tendencies in scientific practices and global disparities in citation flows. Geographical proximity has been shown to influence collaboration and citation rates, yet how this affects global patterns remains unclear. Addressing this gap, we examine the interplay of geography and country-level effects in collaboration and citations using OpenAlex data. Analysing 1.6 million publications with 6.8 million collaborations, and 3.7 million citations, we unveil distinct distance dependencies and country-level effects. Collaborations between countries decline slower with distance compared to intra-country collaborations. Surprisingly, citations between countries display lower distance dependence above a certain threshold, while intra-country citations decrease notably. These findings suggest that geographical factors alone do not determine inter-country collaborations and citations, hinting at underlying country-level effects that we will explore further in follow-up research. This study advances our understanding of the complex dynamics shaping international scientific engagement.

Keywords: International Collaboration; International Citation; Scientific Practice; Geography

1. Introduction

In recent decades, the landscape of scientific collaboration has undergone substantial transformations, marked by a notable rise in international collaboration (Marginson, 2022). Despite this trend, there remains an ongoing debate regarding the degree to which scientific endeavours are influenced by national boundaries. Scholars have noted a tendency to cite “compatriots”, suggesting a bias towards national affiliations in scholarly discourse (Larivière et al., 2018). Moreover, concerns have been raised regarding the unequal distribution of citation flows globally, highlighting issues of scholarly inequality (Gomez et al., 2022; Nielsen et al., 2021). At the same time, studies have demonstrated a clear dependence of collaboration and citation rates on geographical distance (Isfandyari-Moghaddam et al., 2023; Pan et al., 2012). However, the intricate interplay between geography and scientific practices, both within and between countries, remains insufficiently understood. Indeed, some earlier findings of “country biases” might be confounded by geography in a potentially complex way. That is, distance not only affects collaborations and citations between countries, but a growing scientific enterprise within a country may also affect local opportunities for collaboration and citation. This complexity underscores the need for a detailed examination of how collaboration and citation patterns are influenced by geography at various levels.

In this study, we investigate the role of geography and country-level effects in shaping collaboration and citation dynamics. This study aims to elucidate how collaboration and citation patterns evolve in response to geographical distance, comparing patterns within countries to

between countries. By exploring these dynamics, we seek to provide insights into the interaction between geography and scholarly engagement in an increasingly connected world.

2. Methods

Our analysis draws upon data from core publications¹ in OpenAlex, employing publications from 2018 to analyse collaboration patterns and citation data to publications in 2008 to examine citation relationships. We examined a grand total of 1,641,368 publications, comprising 6,772,034 collaborations and 3,702,173 citations. We only considered cities with at least one publication in 2018, resulting in affiliations from 218 countries and 10,549 cities. Given the latitude and longitude coordinates of two points, we calculated the geodesic distance between them using the Haversine formula.

3. Results

We first examine the overarching influence of geography on collaboration and citation dynamics, as illustrated in Fig. 1A and 1B. It is evident that as geographical distance increases, for both inter-city collaboration and citation the probability of a link exhibits a power-law decay. The impact of geographical distance appears more pronounced on collaboration than on citation probabilities. Furthermore, a gravity model seems to reasonably fit both collaboration and citation networks (Fig. 1C and 1D).

Figure 1: Effect of geographic distance on the international collaboration and citation networks. The x -axis always refers to geographical distance. (A) probability of a collaboration link between cities; (B) probability of a citation link between cities; (C) relative weight of collaborations between cities; (D) relative weight of citations between cities.

We now explore how geographical patterns of collaboration and citation differ within and between countries, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The decay rate of the collaboration probability with distance is less steep for inter-country collaborations compared to intra-country collaborations. Additionally, we observe a substantial difference between intra-country and inter-country

¹ <https://open.leidenranking.com/information/indicators>

collaboration probabilities under similar distance conditions (Fig. 2A, 2C).

Citation rates between countries demonstrate a lower dependence on distance ($b = -0.09$), except for short distances. Conversely, there is a discernible trend of decreasing citation rates within countries with increasing distance ($b = -0.16$) (Fig. 2B, 2D).

Figure 2: Geographical patterns of collaboration and citation differ within and between countries. Plot layout follows Fig. 1: (A) collaboration probability; (B) citation probability; (C) collaboration weight; (D) citation weight.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The differential impact of geography on collaboration and citation patterns underscores the complex interplay between spatial proximity and scholarly interactions. Our findings corroborate that collaboration and citation patterns are influenced by geographical distance. However, these patterns are not solely determined by geographical factors; country-level influences also seem to play a substantial role. The observed difference between inter-country and intra-country collaboration and citation points to the presence of distinct mechanisms operating at multiple levels. Country-level factors may include a nation's research strength (including quantity and quality of research output) and language barriers. Moving forward, we aim to investigate these country-level effects in more detail. Our study contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the evolving landscape of scientific research in an increasingly interconnected world.

Open science practices

Data and code are planned to be shared after the completion of the study.

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Author contributions

Leyan Wu: Data curation, Formal Analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft

Akrati Saxena: Writing – review & editing

Vincent Trrag: Conceptualization, Methodology, Project administration, Writing – review & editing

Competing interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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